

The Tunnel-of-Why: A Structural Causal Modeling Approach to Safety Analysis in Socio-Technical Systems

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Abstract

This paper introduces the *Tunnel-of-Why*, a structured method for incident analysis that addresses the hindsight bias and reductionism common in traditional approaches. Grounded in the principles of Safety-II, it assumes that individuals typically act rationally within their context, and that failures arise from the same adaptive mechanisms that usually ensure success. To formalize this reasoning, we employ Structural Causal Models (SCM) as developed by Pearl, using the *do*-operator to represent interventions and enable counterfactual reasoning. A worked example in software verification illustrates how the *Tunnel-of-Why* reveals hidden assumptions, models them as exogenous variables, and evaluates process improvements formally. By integrating human-centered inquiry with rigorous causal modeling, the *Tunnel-of-Why* offers a method that is both theoretically robust and practically applicable to complex socio-technical systems, thereby contributing to ongoing advances in safety science.

Introduction

Safety analysis in socio-technical systems faces a recurring dilemma: adverse events seem obvious in hindsight yet were far from predictable beforehand. Classical root cause analyses (RCA, 5-Whys, Ishikawa diagrams) often reduce complex event chains to linear cause–effect stories. While these tools support accountability, they risk oversimplification and may reinforce a blame culture.

Modern safety science takes a different view, emphasizing that most operations succeed despite variability, uncertainty, and complexity. Safety-II (Hollnagel, 2014) and the Just Culture perspective (Dekker, 2014; Marx, 2001) argue that people usually act reasonably within their context. Failures are not deliberate deviations but unintended outcomes of otherwise adaptive performance.

This paper introduces the *Tunnel-of-Why* as an approach to analyze such events. It combines:

1. Retrospective reconstruction of processes.
2. Prospective exploration of possible outcomes under varying conditions.
3. A forward-looking resilience perspective that acknowledges the importance of assumptions, awareness, and context alongside procedures.

To provide mathematical rigor, we model the Tunnel-of-Why using Structural Causal Models (SCM) (Pearl, 2009). SCM offers a formal language to represent endogenous variables, exogenous influences, causal fields, and interventions. This makes it possible not only to explain past events but also to test process improvements in a systematic way.

Related Work

Traditional safety analysis relies on **retrospective methods** such as Root Cause Analysis (RCA), Ishikawa diagrams, and the “5 Whys.” These techniques reconstruct causal chains leading to an adverse outcome and are useful for identifying latent organizational, technical, and human factors. Models such as Reason’s Swiss Cheese Model (Reason, 1997) and Hollnagel’s Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM) (Hollnagel, 2012) extend this view by emphasizing barrier interactions, performance variability, and systemic weaknesses. However, retrospective methods have a fundamental limitation: they are conducted with full knowledge of the outcome and are therefore prone to hindsight bias. Events that seem obvious in hindsight may not have been foreseeable beforehand, leading to simplified narratives and misplaced accountability.

To anticipate failures before they occur, **prospective methods** such as Fault Tree Analysis (FTA), Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA), and Event Tree Analysis (ETA) were introduced.

- FTA deduces top-level system failures from logical combinations of lower-level events.
- FMEA systematically examines potential component failures and their consequences.
- ETA starts with an initiating event and maps potential outcome sequences.

These techniques allow **a systematic anticipation of failures** and the prioritization of risk mitigation. Yet they remain limited by their assumptions: they can only address failures that are already known or considered plausible. They struggle to capture emergent behaviors, novel couplings, or “unknown unknowns” characteristic of complex socio-technical systems.

Recognizing these limits, **modern safety science** emphasizes systemic and adaptive approaches (for an overview, see Karanikas, Zerguine, 2024).

- **Resilience Engineering** (Hollnagel, Woods, Leveson, 2006) focuses on how systems adapt, absorb, and recover from disruptions.
- **STAMP/CAST** (Leveson, 2012, Leveson, 2020) frames accidents as control problems shaped by inadequate constraints and emergent interactions.
- **Safety-II** (Hollnagel, 2014) shifts attention from what goes wrong to what usually goes right, emphasizing everyday successful performance.
- **Safety III** (Leveson, 2020, Aven 2021) shifts attention from what goes right in daily work (Safety II) to how complex socio-technical systems are designed and controlled so they can adapt, stay resilient, and avoid unacceptable losses under uncertain conditions.
- **High Reliability Organization theory (HRO)** (Weick & Sutcliffe, 2007) highlights mindfulness and collective responsiveness in high-risk operations.
- **Just Culture** (Dekker, 2014; Marx, 2001) emphasizes balancing accountability with openness, enabling individuals to report errors without fear of disproportionate punishment.

- **Normalization of deviance** (Vaughan, 1996) and **migration to the boundary** (Amalberti, 2013) describe how cultural drift and pursuit of efficiency gradually erode safety margins.

Parallel to these developments, **Structural Causal Models (SCM)** introduced by Pearl (2009) have transformed causal reasoning in statistics and artificial intelligence. SCM provides a formal basis for modeling causal structures, testing interventions with the *do*-operator, and reasoning counterfactually. Despite their broad application elsewhere, SCMs have rarely been applied in safety science. This paper contributes to bridging that gap by integrating SCM with the Tunnel-of-Why method, combining resilience-oriented inquiry with formal causal modeling.

The Tunnel-of-Why

The Tunnel-of-Why is grounded in the idea that failures emerge not from irrational behavior but from reasonable actions within specific contexts. It avoids hindsight bias by reconstructing events as they were experienced, emphasizing assumptions, beliefs, and constraints rather than linear cause–effect chains. The method is built on eight axioms:

1. **Normal Performance** – Individuals generally act correctly, following procedures and norms as they understand them.
2. **Contextual Rationality** – Actions are rational relative to available knowledge, goals, and situational constraints.
3. **Event Deviation** – Failures and successes stem from the same adaptive mechanisms.
4. **Procedural Trajectory** – Events unfold as sequences of actions, procedures, and contextual conditions.
5. **Forward–Backward Duality** – Analysis requires both backward tracing (from outcomes to origins) and forward reconstruction (from decisions to outcomes).
6. **Non-counterfactual Learning** – Analyses must avoid trivial “if–then” hindsight reasoning.
7. **Recognition Gap** – Failures often occur because deviations were not recognized at the time, rather than because actions were irrational.
8. **Narrative Coherence** – Analyses should reconstruct events as coherent stories, beginning with the actors’ lived context rather than the final outcome.

The Tunnel-of-Why is implemented as a structured procedure:

1. **Baseline reconstruction** – Establish what is normally done, based on procedures and rules.
2. **Event-centered focus** – Identify the undesired event and situate it against the baseline.
3. **Back propagation** – Trace the process backwards from the undesired event to reconstruct its trajectory.
4. **Forward propagation** – Reconstruct how individuals acted in context and how their actions contributed to the outcome.

5. **Feedback loop** – Evaluate whether different assumptions or awareness could have changed the trajectory, without reducing the analysis to simplistic error attribution.

This approach integrates narrative inquiry with formal reasoning, ensuring that countermeasures address systemic issues rather than assigning blame. IEC 62740 (IEC 62740, 2015) lists numerous techniques for root cause analysis. What they have in common is that they start from the undesired event and work backwards to identify the root cause. The “Tunnel of Why,” however, takes a different approach. It begins by asking what the normal procedure was - that is, the standard process people usually follow. This avoids a hindsight-blaming culture, since people generally act correctly in the moment. From there, the analysis moves forward along the timeline, asking why, at a specific point, a certain choice was made—even though an alternative path might have been possible if it had been known. Instead of reasoning backwards, the investigator attempts to step into the shoes of the individuals involved, always asking within their context why they acted (normally correctly) in that way, and what different behavior could have led to a positive outcome.

Structural Causal Modeling of Operational Procedures

To rigorously analyze operational safety in socio-technical systems, we apply the framework of **Structural Causal Models (SCM)** as introduced by Pearl (2000, 2009). An SCM distinguishes between **exogenous variables U** which capture influences outside the model; **endogenous variables V** which represent system states and decisions determined within the model; and **structural functions F** , which encode the causal relationships linking variables. Each endogenous variable is defined by a structural equation of the form $V_i = f_i(Pa(V_i), U_i)$, where $Pa(V_i)$ denotes its direct causes. This formalism provides both mathematical and graphical language for causality, connecting equations to **causal diagrams** (directed acyclic graphs). Within this framework, interventions are represented by the **do-operator $do(\cdot)$** , which modifies the structural equations by fixing a variable to a chosen value and thereby allows counterfactual reasoning about “what would happen if” scenarios. This approach enables us to formally represent how inputs, preconditions, roles, tools, and contextual factors jointly determine outcomes, and how system properties change under interventions (Pearl, 2009).

A **Structural Causal Model (SCM)** is defined as a tuple

$$\mathcal{M} = \langle U, V, F \rangle$$

where:

- U is a set of exogenous variables with $U_i \in U$, determined outside the model,
- V is a set of endogenous variables with $V_i \in V$, determined within the model,
- $F = \{f_V : Pa(V) \cup U_V \rightarrow V\}$ a set of functions $V_i = f_i(Pa(V_i), U_i), \forall V_i \in V$ which structurally connects V_i with all related parent variables $Pa(V_i)$ determining the outcome of V_i given any unknown disturbances by variable U_i .

The parents of an endogenous Variable $V_i \in V$ are called the direct cause of V_i . In this paper, without loss of generality, we treat the variables as propositions that can take the truth values *true* (1) or *false* (0). The variables are expressed as propositional logic expressions, while the

structural equations themselves constitute propositional logic formulas that define how these variables are causally related.

Structural equation modeling mathematically formalizes a Structural Causal Model (SCM). In this framework, the endogenous variable on the left-hand side of each equation represents the effect, while the right-hand side specifies its direct causes under a given causal field CF_i for V_i that is, the relevant context given by a set of exogenous variables $U_i^k \in \mathbf{U}$ in which a cause can produce its effect. Exogenous variables capture the known unknowns: factors outside the modeled system that influence outcomes but are not explicitly represented as endogenous components.

Example

$V_1 = \text{switch is ON}, V_2 = \text{bulb flashes (lights)}$

$$V_1 = U_1 \wedge CF_1, V_2 = V_1 \wedge CF_2.$$

If the switch is on - regardless of the reason, whether it was turned by a human operator or accidentally activated (e.g., by an object falling on it - this is represented by the exogenous variable U_1 that is the starting event which is not explicitly modeled in the SCM, which sets $V_1 = 1$. In this case, the variable is true. The causal fields CF_1 and CF_2 assumed to be initially 1 so as not to block the parent variable that causes Variable V_2 . Consequently, V_2 becomes true, meaning that the bulb flashes.

If the bulb does not flash, although the switch is on, one would examine the exogenous variables that may be blocking the causal influence of V_2 . Here, are some $U_p \in \{0,1\}$ = main power available (1 = powered), $U_h \in \{0,1\}$ = bulb healthy (1 = intact filament/LED driver OK), $U_s \in \{0,1\}$ = short circuit not present, $U_a \in \{0,1\}$ = agent/operator intent (drives the switch). Finally, this would lead to $CF_2 = U_p \wedge U_h \wedge U_s \wedge U_a$.

If one of the exogenous variables is false, the bulb will not flash. Note that the exogenous variables are not explicitly defined in the initial model, as they are not known a priori. Once they become known, however, they can be represented directly as part of a causal context $CF_2 = U_p \wedge U_h \wedge U_s \wedge U_a$ leading to $V_2 = (V_1 \wedge CF_2)$. This context must be conjunctively linked to the endogenous variable—meaning not causally sufficient on its own, but necessary for the effect to occur. Alternatively, disjunctively linked reasons can be represented, each of which may independently permit the effect.

Note that even when the causal context is known, an exogenous variable is still modeled as such. Complete knowledge of the causal context would imply complete knowledge of the world, which is not realistically attainable. In Pearl's framework, exogenous variables remain essential because they capture the uncertainty, incompleteness, and unobserved influences of the model. Even if parts of the context become observable and can be incorporated into the endogenous structure, the remaining unknowns are still represented as exogenous inputs. This distinction preserves the causal semantics of the model, allowing it to remain valid even under partial knowledge of the world.

The distinction between an exogenous variable and a causal field can be described as follows. A causal field is defined as the conjunction of multiple exogenous variables, representing the contextual conditions under which a cause can bring about its effect. However, when a particular contextual factor needs to be made explicit—for example, to test whether the presence or absence of that factor determines whether the effect occurs—it can be modeled individually as an exogenous variable. Thus, while an endogenous variable represents an

observable event that functions as a cause for a subsequent effect, the exogenous variables—either explicitly modeled or aggregated within the causal field—capture the contextual conditions necessary for that cause to realize its effect.

The **do-Operator**, denoted $do(X = x) \ x \in \{0,1\}$, represents an intervention that sets a variable X to a fixed value x , independently of its usual causal parents.

$$\mathcal{M}_{do(X=x)} = \langle \mathbf{U}, \mathbf{V}, \mathbf{F}' \rangle \text{ with } \mathbf{F}' = (\mathbf{F} \setminus f_X) \cup \{X := x\}.$$

The original structural equation for variable X is removed and replaced with the assignment $X := x$. This expresses the semantics of an intervention: we explicitly force X to take the value x , thereby breaking any incoming causal arrows into X , regardless of its parent variables or associated exogenous factors.

Let us assume in the above example a third Variable $V_3 = (V_1 \wedge V_2) \wedge U_3$ in the structural model \mathcal{M}

For example, a supervisor might check whether the switch is turned on and the bulb is flashing. The check returns *true* only if both conditions hold. Formally, we can write this as $V_3 \in \{0,1\} = \textit{both switch and bulb is okay}$, where $V_3 = 1$ represents the case in which both the switch and the bulb are functioning correctly. The role of this supervisor is to ensure that the bulb does not flash unintentionally, but only when the switch is on.

Suppose someone switches on the bulb. Under normal circumstances, this would set $V_1 = 1$. But if we intervene using the *do*-operator to enforce $do(V_1 = 0)$. This forces V_1 to remain false, regardless of the operator's action. In other words, the intervention "cuts" the causal link from the switch to V_1 , ensuring that the bulb does not turn on, even though the switch has been flipped.

Without the *do*-operator, we only observe the system as defined by its structural equations. If the switch variable V_1 is defective, an operator may believe the switch has been turned on $V_1 = 1$, but in fact the bulb variable V_2 does not turn on. In this case, the supervisor variable V_3 which checks whether both V_1 and V_2 are true, will evaluate to false. The defect is not directly visible to the operator, because they only see the attempt to set $V_1 = 1$, not the broken causal link between V_1 and V_2 .

With the *do*-operator, by contrast, we intervene and set $do(V_1 = 0)$. This forces V_1 to remain *false*, regardless of what the operator does, and cuts all incoming arrows into V_1 . As a result, the supervisor variable V_3 also evaluates to *false*, since one of the required conditions is missing. This illustrates how intervention actively changes the causal structure, allowing us to distinguish between observational patterns and genuine causal influence. Here, the correct functioning of the supervisor V_3 was verified by intervention.

Tunnel-Of-Why – The Mathematical Foundation

The Tunnel-of-Why approach seeks to overcome a central limitation: the epistemic problem of what can be known under incomplete knowledge. Within the language of Structural Causal Models (Pearl, 2000; 2009), this corresponds to the role of exogenous variables. These variables represent factors outside the formal model that nevertheless influence outcomes. Because they are not explicitly known at the outset, uncovering them requires engagement with practitioners and domain experts—typically through interviews with the roles involved in the

process. Such an inquiry can reveal assumptions, oversights, or contextual factors that were not directly modeled but nonetheless shaped the course of events.

Assuming that in most cases procedures are carried out correctly, the cause of an undesired event may lie not in incorrect actions but in something overlooked or in an assumption that did not hold true. The Tunnel-of-Why is represented as an SCM and supports investigation by analogy to a tunnel with multiple branching paths. At each junction, the analyst asks: *why was this path taken and not another?* This iterative questioning process surfaces the hidden influences that, in SCM terms, correspond to exogenous variables. By integrating these factors into the analysis, the Tunnel-of-Why complements formal causal modeling by systematically identifying the unmodeled but necessary context conditions that enable or block causal pathways.

It is important to note that the investigation relies heavily on documented processes and clearly defined role descriptions, particularly using **Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)**, as well as interviews with the individuals involved in each process. These interviews are conducted in a structured manner, guided by clearly defined input and output expectations and the relevant causal context - that is, the specific conditions that must be met for the correct tasks to be performed. Building on this, there are four possible scenarios that can lead to either the desired or an undesired event. We adopt the terms true positive, true negative, false negative, and false positive in analogy to classification theory, but with definitions tailored to socio-technical processes:

- **True Positive (TP):** the process follows the correct path and leads to the desired outcome.
- **True Negative (TN):** the process follows a wrong path, correctly executed, leading to an undesired outcome.
- **False Negative (FN):** the process follows the correct procedure, but under given conditions no correct path exists, leading to an undesired outcome.
- **False Positive (FP):** the process follows an incorrect path, yet by coincidence the desired outcome still occurs.”

These are illustrated below.

True Positive (TP): Operational procedure followed as planned, leading to the desired event. Both action and outcome are correct.

True Negative (TN): Operational procedure followed as planned, but at a specific point in time a wrong path was chosen and consistently followed, leading to an undesired event. Both action and outcome are incorrect.

False Negative (FN): Operational procedure followed correctly, and actions were contextually appropriate, but under the given circumstances no correct path existed, and the undesired event

occurred. The action is correct, but the outcome is wrong.

False Positive (FP): Operational procedure not correct at a specific point in time, yet the outcome still resulted in the desired event. The action is wrong, but the outcome appears correct.

2. Variables for the Tunnel-Of Why

Exogenous variables represent background conditions not explained within the structural causal model. However, for our approach we adapt the FRAM approach to define the causal field by further refining the exogenous variables U_x^i related to the endogenous variable V_i with

U_{in}^i : factors influencing input data, U_{temp}^i : factors influencing temporal context, U_{cont}^i : factors influencing operational context, U_{prec}^i : factors influencing preconditions, U_{rex}^i : factors influencing execution roles, U_{tex}^i : factors influencing execution tools and resources, U_{rver}^i : factors influencing verification roles, U_{choice}^i : factors influencing action choice, U_{out}^i : factors influencing outcomes.

In practice, the set of exogenous variables is context-dependent and extensible. It must be tailored to the socio-technical and organizational characteristics of the system under study, as illustrated in the example below. The variables presented here serve only as representative examples of key influencing factors. They are typically not modeled within standard process models, yet are known to exert a significant impact on the eventual outcome or effect.

The exogenous variables associated with an endogenous variable V_i can be summarized under a causal field CF_i , which is defined as the conjunction of the exogenous variables specified above: $CF_i = \bigwedge_{j=1}^k U_j^i$. Here, j denotes the index associated with the exogenous variables defined above.

Endogenous Variables are determined by their parents and the causal field with $V_i = f_i(Pa(V_i), CF_i)$. Each V_i represents the output produced by its parent variables $Pa(V_i)$ and the relevant causal field CF_i .

With that said, an if-condition, or a causal branch can be represented by an endogenous variable V_j^c with $V_i^c := V_{i_1}^c \oplus \dots \oplus V_{i_k}^c \dots$ with \oplus exclusive-OR.

With this, the outcome V_i of a process step becomes *true* given the input $P(V_i)$ within a causal context CF_i under the condition V_i^c if $V_i = P(V_i) \wedge V_i^c \wedge CF_i$ is *true*.

Tunnel Of Why – Example Software Testing with Structural Causal Model

Scenario

A software (SW) component must be tested and verified before it can be used in operational service, that is, prior to being handed over for system integration testing under real-world conditions. At the software test level, only a subset of the full range of environmental conditions can be covered. Verifier 1 is aware of this limitation and therefore conducts tests under

simulation and limited field conditions. These constraints are documented in the software test report. Verifier 2, however, receives the tested software together with the release note and assumes general suitability, without realizing that the tests addressed only a specific configuration. The software test report, which contains the explicit limitations, is not included in the delivery package at the start of system integration. Verifier 1 implicitly assumes that Verifier 2 will cover all aspects, especially the external software interfaces, to ensure field compatibility. During the system integration test, which simulates real-world conditions, the untested conditions are finally encountered, and a defect manifests.”

Variables and structural equations

- Endogenous variables with 0:=false, and 1:=true:
 $V_1 \in \{0,1\}$: SW passes test (under executed test context)
 $V_2 \in \{0,1\}$: Release decision to use
- Causal field / context:
 $CF_{sw_test} \in \{0,1\}$: **Actual** SW tested according to SW specification and processes
 $CF_{sys_test} \in \{0,1\}$: **Actual** system test coverage field condition
 $\widehat{CF}_{sys_test} \in \{0,1\}$: Actual system/ field not coverage condition (but not known)
- Exogenous variables:
 $U_1 \in \{0,1\}$: Exogenous variables for software testing start
 $U_{awareness} \in \{0,1\}$: Verifier-2 awareness of SW test limits
- Structural Equations
 $V_1 = U_1 \wedge CF_{sw_test}$
 $V_2 = [V_1 \wedge (CF_{sys_test})] \vee V_1 \wedge [\widehat{CF}_{sys_test} \wedge \neg U_{awareness}]$

The causal field CF_{sys_test} represents system tests that fully cover the relevant field conditions, thereby closing the gaps left by software-only testing. In contrast, the alternative causal field \widehat{CF}_{sys_test} denotes that a system test was performed, but without covering all field conditions—leaving residual gaps. This situation would not necessarily pose a problem as long as Verifier 2 is aware of these limitations. However, if such awareness is absent ($\neg U_{awareness} = 1$), the software may still be released: $CF_{sys_test} = 0$, but $\widehat{CF}_{sys_test} = 1$ (partial test present), leading to an undesired release decision. The causal fields CF_{sys_test} and \widehat{CF}_{sys_test} are mutually exclusive. If $CF_{sys_test} = 1$ then $\widehat{CF}_{sys_test} = 0$ and vice versa.

In the structural equation for V_2 , the first term represents the standard case in which release occurs only when system tests fully cover the field conditions. The second term captures the alternative case, where a product is released despite incomplete coverage of field conditions.

While $U_{awareness}$ is always implicitly present, it is not explicitly represented in the known causal CF_{sys_test} field or in standardized processes and is therefore not modeled in advance. However, through interviews and qualitative inquiry, it often becomes evident that a critical assumption did not hold. At this point, one can further investigate whether this assumption was, in fact, known but not properly communicated - an issue which, in most cases, often turns out to be the underlying cause. Alternatively, it may not have been documented because testers implicitly assumed that it was self-evident that they could not test certain system integration conditions, and that the system integrator would be aware of this limitation.

If this exogenous variable $U_{awareness}$ is identified, it can subsequently be incorporated into the causal field, thereby making explicit what each process must achieve - whether at the software testing level or at the system integration level. In practice, it is the responsibility of system integration to ensure that real-field conditions are adequately represented, at least at the interfaces of the product constituting the system. At the same time, exhaustive software testing should aim to provide maximum coverage of the relevant system properties. However, if all conditions were to be tested solely at the software level, the role of system integration would become redundant, which would contradict established good practice in socio-technical engineering.

Investigators may not initially know all relevant endogenous variables when commencing a Tunnel-of-Why analysis. This limitation can introduce hindsight bias, but only to a limited extent. In safety-critical domains, the processes that specify what must be done and how tasks should be performed are typically standardized. While certain details may be missing in practice, the procedural steps themselves are generally well defined. If such steps were absent, this would constitute a genuine process gap, in which case individual operators cannot reasonably be held accountable. In most investigations, however, the problem does not stem from missing processes but rather from the way existing processes are interpreted and applied. In the present example, Verifier 2 was unaware that specific tests - for instance, the software external interface test—did not fully cover the field conditions. Consequently, their testing focus may have diverged from what was required to ensure full coverage. In our example, it is clear that testing tools must be certified and applicable to the relevant conditions, and that any exclusions should be documented in application rules, test reports or other documents. In practice, the challenge is not that requirements are absent or undocumented, but that critical information may be buried in extensive documentation. As a result, assumptions made by one actor may not be shared, understood, or visible to others.

This is where the strength of the Tunnel-of-Why method lies: it recognizes that people generally act correctly within their roles. Therefore, blame is neither useful nor justified. The challenges arise in complex socio-technical organizations, where not all assumptions, beliefs, and contextual knowledge are equally distributed or transparent. By asking participants why they chose one course of action rather than another, the Tunnel-of-Why provides insights that differ fundamentally from standard hindsight-oriented techniques such as the ‘5 Whys’ or counterfactual analysis.

Modified Structural Equations

Adding the exogenous variable

$$U_{sw_sys_cover} \in \{0,1\}: \textit{Documented check of sw vrs system test coverage}$$

leads to

$$\begin{aligned} V_1 &= U_1 \wedge CF_{sw_test} \\ V_2 &= [V_1 \wedge (CF_{sys_test} \wedge U_{sw_sys_cover})] \vee V_1 \wedge [\widehat{CF}_{sys_test} \wedge \neg U_{sw_sys_cover} \wedge \neg U_{awareness}] \end{aligned}$$

To ensure robustness in the future, a systematic check should be implemented that explicitly compares the coverage of software tests with that of system tests in order to identify potential gaps. If such a comparison is not carried out, the software must not be released, regardless of any assumptions made by the verifier. In terms of process modeling, this implies that the second conjunctive term in the structural equation for the release decision can be omitted, as release becomes conditional solely on the explicit coverage check rather than on verifier assumptions.

$$V_1 = U_1 \wedge CF_{sw_test}$$

$$V_2 = [V_1 \wedge (CF_{sys_test} \wedge U_{sw_sys_cover})]$$

It is important to note that there is constraint $U_{sw_sys_cover} \leq CF_{sys_test}$. Thus, whenever the

Fig.1 DAG of the modified example: the system is not released until a check between software and system integration testing has been performed.

documented coverage check is true $U_{sw_sys_cover} = 1$, the actual system-test causal field must also be true $CF_{sys_test} = 1$. This encodes precisely the intended verification step: the coverage attestation cannot be positive unless system testing truly matches the relevant field conditions. Figure 1 illustrated the structural equation model using its DAG representation.

Do-operator

Using the *do*-operator, one can formally evaluate the situation in which the verifier is unaware of existing test gaps. Consider the intervention $do(U_{awareness} = 0)$, together with the conditions $CF_{sys_test} = 0$ (system test does not fully cover the field conditions) and $\widehat{CF}_{sys_test} = 1$ (a partial system test is present and perceived as sufficient). If the software tests hold true $V_1 = 1$, the release decision V_2 can only become true if an explicit coverage check has been carried out, that is, when $U_{sw_sys_cover} = 1$. By definition, this implies that $CF_{sys_test} = 1$. Hence, release is only possible when the coverage check establishes actual alignment between software testing and system testing under the relevant field conditions. Otherwise Thus, release is prevented unless coverage is explicitly confirmed, independent of verifier assumptions.

Practical Experience in Applying the Tunnel-of-Why

The Tunnel-of-Why method has been applied in multiple real-world industrial cases. Due to confidentiality restrictions, detailed case data cannot be published, but the experiences summarized here reflect recurring patterns across all applications.

Because the analysis requires considerable effort, the first step is always to understand and thoroughly examine the intended process. The investigation then proceeds by identifying the

starting point and selecting interview partners who actually participated in the process that led to the undesired event. Structured interviews are conducted following the FRAM concept. Typical guiding questions include: What was your input? What was the planned output? Which preconditions were assumed? Were there constraints in time, resources, or tools? Which actions were taken for good reasons given the circumstances at the time, and why?

Since the interviews, evaluations, and derivation of measures demand substantial resources, we applied the Tunnel-of-Why only in cases with significant business impact—either in monetary terms or from a safety perspective.

Several important learnings emerged from these applications. Although the Tunnel-of-Why has a rigorous mathematical foundation, in practice it is implemented in a non-formal way, using pictograms and guiding questions inspired by the FRAM approach. After identifying the starting point of the evaluation, the questions first address process inputs and outputs and then extend to the exogenous variables defined earlier, allowing the analysis to capture assumptions and contextual influences that would otherwise remain hidden.

All interview participants regarded the Tunnel-of-Why as more helpful and respectful than traditional approaches. From the outset, it was made explicit that no individual had acted wrongly. The basic assumption was that each person acted in good faith and did their best within the knowledge and context available at the time. The interviews and subsequent derivation of measures therefore avoided hindsight bias and blame. Instead, the guiding question was always: *What would I have done, given the information and context available at that moment?* Participants appreciated that their perspectives were taken seriously and that they had a genuine voice in the process.

Interestingly, both interviewees and moderators consistently concluded that, under the same circumstances, they would not have acted differently. This is not surprising, since socio-technical processes involve multiple layers of verification in which the work of one person is checked by others. Even if one individual overlooks something, others are normally in place to detect potential failures.

Finally, once the analysis recognizes what went wrong, measures can be defined. These measures can then be informally validated by applying the *do*-operator to the revised process: by intervening on specific variables and causal conditions, one can check whether the new configuration would have prevented the undesired event. In this way, the Tunnel-of-Why does not only reconstruct past events but also provides a structured basis for evaluating future improvements.

These experiences empirically confirm two key axioms of the Tunnel-of-Why: contextual rationality and the recognition gap. Participants consistently emphasized that their actions were reasonable within the context, and that failures arose from unrecognized assumptions rather than individual mistakes.

Conclusion

This paper introduced the Tunnel-of-Why as a structured method for analyzing socio-technical events, combining axiomatic foundations, structural causal modeling, and practical application. The approach advances safety analysis by moving beyond hindsight-driven explanations and counterfactual reasoning, instead reconstructing events from the actors' perspective and explicitly modeling exogenous variables and causal fields. In doing so, it

integrates Safety-II principles with Pearl's structural causal models, enabling both retrospective understanding and prospective testing of process improvements through the *do*-operator.

The method has been applied in several industrial cases, consistently demonstrating its value for uncovering hidden assumptions, bridging perspectives across organizational roles, and supporting learning without blame. Due to confidentiality restrictions, detailed case data cannot be disclosed; however, the aggregated observations reported here reflect recurring patterns across applications.

Several limitations remain. The present work is conceptual and exploratory, and further systematic validation is needed across diverse domains. Confidentiality constraints limit the availability of detailed case material, and no quantitative evaluation has yet been conducted.

Author Contributions (CRediT Taxonomy)

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- **Methodology:** Lazos Filippidis
- **Formal analysis:** Lazos Filippidis
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